

What we want to do differently?

Anaerobic digestion is one interesting option to handle sludge effectively while producing valuable products. Several pulp mills are already treating the sludge in this approach. However, it has its own operational issues. In this project a biorefinery approach will be developed where torrefaction is integrated with anaerobic digestion to produce multiple products such as energy carriers (methane and biochar) and platform chemicals, for example organic acids.

* Torrefaction is a process where material is heated in the temperature range of 200 – 300 °C in the inert environment. It is same like baking food in our domestic ovens but in a controlled environment.

* Anaerobic digestion is a process of treating organic material with microbes, which produces a flammable gas known as biogas.

Expected impacts:

What are the societal benefits?

- Allows to create new employment in rural areas.
- Improved resource efficiency.
- Improves the environment by reducing dependency on fossil fuels.
- Improves EU's competitiveness in biobased products manufacturing.

What are the benefits to the Pulp industry?

- Adds a new value chain to the existing pulp mill.
- Demonstrates an integrated process to handle pulp industry sludge.
- Diversify the application of pulp industry sludge.
- Improves the environmental feasibility and competitiveness of European pulp industry.

TOPIS- BioCirc project closely aligns with the following sustainable development goals:

TOPIS-BioCirc

Sludge: waste no more; Its a resource

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TOPIS-BioCirc

Sludge: waste no more; Its a resource

Integrating torrefaction of pulp and paper industry sludge with microbial conversion: A new approach to produce bioenergy carriers and biochemicals

Funded by the European Union

Background

Pulp industry is one of the major industry in the EU region in terms of employment and economy. More importantly pulp industry provides employment in rural areas. Pulp industry is also known for consuming large quantities of natural resources and producing huge amounts of wastes. On the other hand, pulp industry in EU is facing challenges like reducing demand of paper, increasing competitiveness and strict environmental regulations etc. In order to address some of these challenges, pulp mills are aiming to produce multiple products such as district heating, electricity, bark, lignin, packaging, nanocellulose and biochemicals under forest biorefinery. Handling the waste generated at pulp mills following strict environmental guidelines is another challenge.

Pulp mills produce large quantities of wastewater and sludge. The modern pulp mills produce around 40 - 50 kg of sludge per ton of dry paper produced. This sludge has two faces, on one side its a big challenge to handle and on the other side it is a great source of organic matter.

Overview of the project

TOPIS-Biocirc aims at developing strategies to produce high value products from pulp industry sludge.

This project demonstrates a torrefaction centric biorefinery approach to produce organic acids and energy carriers from pulp industry sludge. The economic and environmental feasibility of such process will also be established.

EU Pulp industry statistics for 2020

Pulp production:

Total amount of pulp mills = 894

Total amount of pulp produced = 36.2 million tonnes

Employment and economics:

Total turnover: 83 billion

Total amount of jobs: 179,647

Resources used:

Total amount of wood used = 108.6 million tonnes

Total amount of water used (2019) = 3758 million m³

Wastes produced in a pulp mill

In a pulp mill different types of wastes are produced at different stages in the whole manufacturing process of pulp and subsequent products.

What is sludge and how it is handled today?

Sludge at pulp mill is produced during the wastewater treatment. Generally, there are three different type of sludge produced in a pulp mill.

* Data is from Key Statistics Report 2019 of European association representing the paper industry (Cepi)